

D2.5 LEA Innovation procurement ROADMAP in education towards 2030

Final product of LEA project demonstrating innovation procurement as an important co-creation strategy upfront for European digital learning

Date 30 of June 2020

Project acronym: LEA

Project title: Learning Technology Accelerator

Grant Agreement number: 779803

Coordinator: Jyvaskylan Yliopisto

Project funded by the European Commission, H2020

Funding Scheme: H2020-ICT-2017-1

Due date of deliverable:	M 28 30 of June 2020
Actual submission date:	M 28 30 of June 2020
Start date of the project:	March 1, 2018
Project duration:	28 months

Work package	2
Task(s)	T2.5 LEA roadmap
Lead beneficiary	EU Projektkonsult AB (EUPK)
Editor/ authors	EUPK, Task leaders of LEA
Quality reviewers	JYU, ICLEI

Dissemination level		
PU	Public	x
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

This publication LEA D2.5 ROADMAP reflects only the views of the author. The Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Introduction to LEA roadmap.....	4
2. Innovation procurement as strategic co-creation business model in education	5
3. LEA – N Buyers Network, a critical mass of learning technology buyers	12
4. LEA procurement tool and demand towards 2030	16
5. LEA country profiles	19
6. Learning technology market foresight 2030	24
7. The Covid-19 Crisis	28
8. Best practice PCP project design	30
9. Best practice PPI project design	36
10. Cross-sectorial innovation procurement	40
11. School labs and CO – CREATION	43
12. Capacity building concepts	46
13. Exploitation strategy 2020 and beyond	49
14. Final words – Education and innovation procurement upfront 2030	52

GLOSSARY/ ABBREVIATIONS

Buyers network	A critical mass / number of buyers of learning technology with capacity to influence suppliers and the market jointly as a network
Innovation procurement	Innovative methods and processes to procure learning technology and to procure innovations
Procurement tool	An online tool for the buyers network to collect common needs and investments for learning technology
Procurement country profiles	A list of the member states procurement profiles and status to support the market and companies to better understand European procurers of learning technology
PCP	Pre-commercial procurement (PCP) is public procurement of research and development (R&D) services. It is an important tool to stimulate innovation as it enables the public sector to steer the development of new solutions directly towards its needs.
PPI	Public Procurement of Innovative Solutions (PPI) occurs when the public sector uses its purchasing power to act as early adopter of innovative solutions which are not yet available on a large-scale commercial basis.
Cross sectorial PCP	PCP that can be carried out and shared among different sectors e.g. Education with health and employment to stimulate more companies and to raise and share larger sums of investments
School labs	Venues created with a specific methodology that enables dialogue between industry and schools
Capacity building concept	Webinars, seminars, online course, videos and other material LEA has created and shared on the web page to increase competence and awareness of innovation procurement
Exploitation Strategy	A strategy on how LEA partners together with LEA network of buyers will proceed with collaboration after project ends

1. Introduction to LEA Roadmap

Abstract

The LEA project 2018 – 2020 www.learntechaccelerator.eu has developed, implemented and evaluated tools, concepts and models to strengthen **innovation procurement** in education for Europe.

Innovation procurement is a **new purchase and co -creation model** for schools to achieve improved digital learning and results.

The LEA roadmap seeks to provide capacity building and inspire European schools to create similar actions upfront and aligned with UN Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 4, Quality in Education 2030.

Purpose

This is the final product of the LEA project (funded by European Commission 2018 – 2020) and its intention is to provide valuable information on how to continue with innovative procurement of learning technology and the LEA network (LEA-N) after the project ends in June 2020. It shall provide and highlight evidence valid enough to make European procurers of learning technology confident to continue the implementation of innovation procurement with other sources of funding and maintain sustainable long-lasting collaboration upfront.

Use

In education, current buying and procuring practices were designed for print-based learning material, not modern technology. The result is that at times, teachers and students don't end up with the best learning technology tools to meet their needs. The LEA findings provide valuable information on improved learning technology purchase methods and business models for the learning technology eco -system towards 2030.

Method

The LEA Roadmap includes a series of relevant topics described with challenges identified, how LEA overcome them, methods, tools and analysis for progress, results, conclusions and recommendations.

Target groups

The findings shall serve buyers at a local, regional and national level in all Member States (MS) as well as the suppliers of learning technology in Europe.

Location of the complete capacity building material

All material presented in this Innovation procurement roadmap for education (templates, methodologies, guidelines, films, online courses and webinars) can be found at: www.learntechaccelerator.eu

2. Innovation procurement as strategic co-creation business model in education

WHY innovation procurement in Education?

In education the current buying and procuring practices were designed for print-based learning material, not modern technology. The result is that at times, teachers and students don't end up with the best learning technology tools to meet their needs.

Digitalisation of schools is based upon the following three processes and steps;

1. Purchase / procurement process
2. Implementation process
3. Management process

If the first step of purchase and procurement results in the “wrong” digital products and systems, the following two steps will automatically fail. To put it simply, to be successful and reach increased learning results in the digital age, we need to start by building competence and capacity in the digital purchase and procurement process.

Figure 1: Illustration of purchase / procurement process impact

One new tool that has proven successful in the modernization of digital learning material and create a rupture of traditional organisation structures composed by traditional roles performing traditional tasks is INNOVATION PROCUREMENT.

With the LEA project several procuring organisations in Europe have implemented and learned about two innovative models and methods to procure.

- PCP – pre commercial procurement <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/pre-commercial-procurement>
- PPI – public procurement of innovative solutions <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/public-procurement-innovative-solutions>

However innovation procurement (PCP and PPI) is not only an innovative method to purchase and procure the right digital learning tools and services, it also offers many other concepts that can be used to enhance digital learning.

Such tools and concepts are opening up **the sharing of knowledge using innovative collaboration systems, co-creation, user driven digital learning overall and early tests of innovative products and services in real classrooms** together with students and teachers. Additionally LEA project research in spring 2020 during the onset of the COVID-19 crisis showed that teachers that had participated in PCP projects were prepared both with their tools, competences and confidence to teach online in a situation that requires extreme flexibility.

Background and challenges identified

Innovation procurement is a new tool, and all novelties require time and patience to be implemented. Starting up the LEA project, a **group of challenges to adoption of innovation procurement in European schools** were identified and they have been addressed with tasks and analytical work throughout the project period.

Challenges identified in digital education	LEA concept developed and implemented
Lack of Buyers network in education sector with a focus on accelerating uptake and pooling demand for innovative Learntech	LEA Network of procurers
High complexity of challenges in the educational system such as lack of teachers, school dropouts, challenges with technical teaching and learning aids and a missing network for innovation procurement to solve potential identified challenges	LEA procurement idea tool
Lack of information about the procurement procedures of each EU Member State and about the details of the demand side of learning technology procurement	LEA country profiles on procurement
Lack of prediction and understanding of innovative technology among procurers to be able to purchase the solutions of tomorrow	LEA global market foresight 2030, capacity building actions and think tanks
Lack of support on understanding and how to design	PCP methodology

successful PCP implementation for education	Film PCP in 5 steps LEA experts to support European procurers
Lack of support on understanding and how to design successful PPI implementation	PPI methodology Film PPI in 4 steps LEA experts to support European procurers
Innovations within existing learntech industry boundaries are becoming less effective. The potential of product improvements and cost reductions are in most cases already exhausted. Education collaborates with other public administrations and these shall seek to combine the digital innovation investments.	Pre-analysis of a possible cross sectorial PCP between education, health and employment sector in 3 countries
Lack of funding as risk investments for procurers	LEA funding reports and recommendations
Lack of "easy to understand " value of PCP / PPI actions and knowledge to increase capacity and implementation of the actions	LEA capacity building concepts , online courses and webinars
Risk that collaboration and exchange initiated by LEA-N ends when project ends.	LEA Exploitation Strategy

Table 1: challenges and LEA tools developed

The LEA Roadmap contains the complete set of challenges identified, explanation on how we addressed them and presentation of unique tools to address them. All these tools shall serve the European learning technology community upfront towards 2030.

Innovation procurement aligned with foresights on education towards 2030

To serve the European schools in the future, LEA lessons learned and experienced needs to be additionally aligned with important key words and concepts. And according to foresights and strategies of Horizon Europe 2021 - 2028 some of the highlighted ones are:

- Open knowledge system and co-creation
- UN SDG 4 - Quality Education
- Mission oriented approach for education

Open Knowledge system

BOHEMIA is the main EU strategic foresight study in support of the Commission's proposal for Horizon Europe – the EU framework programme for research and innovation 2021 – 2028.

According to the Foresights scenarios BOHEMIA **Open Knowledge Systems** are reality in 2040 <https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/support-policy-making/support-eu-research-and-innovation->

[policy-making/foresight/activities/current/bohemia_en](#). Opening up science, education and innovation prevail across Europe and in large parts of the world.

In 2040 generic technologies such as artificial intelligence and distributed ledger (blockchain) provide the new infrastructure for representing, accessing and using data, information and knowledge. These infrastructures were shaped by public investment in research and innovation from the beginning, and are thus designed in line with principles of openness and transparency. This open infrastructure system will make it possible for producers, consumers, trade, citizens, scientists, policy makers and the relevant organisations to be on the same level of information and to have access to relevant data in real-time. The open, collaborative knowledge system promises to be an important contributor to the European society and economy. Co-creation (companies and customers jointly developing a product) has become the most prevalent form of innovation by manufacturers

Innovation procurement is a tool that enables and encourages **co-creation between schools, municipalities and suppliers** through joint development and tests of user-driven innovative learning technology in classrooms

UN Sustainable Development Goals and the 2030 Agenda

The strategy to achieve Europe's objectives with the next program period are all aligned with the UN SDGs and Agenda 2030 as an umbrella https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/SDG_4_-_Quality_education Monitoring SDG 4 on **quality in education** in an EU context focuses on basic education, tertiary education and adult learning. In particular **early school leaving** and under **achievement in maths, reading and science** are common challenges that Europe needs to tackle to fulfil the UN SDGs in education.

Indicator	Long-term trend (past 15 years)	Short-term trend (past 5 years)
Basic education		
🕒 Early leavers from education and training	↑	↗
🕒 Participation in early childhood education	↑	↑
🕒 Underachievement in reading, maths and science	↓ ⁽¹⁾	↓ ⁽²⁾
Young people neither in employment nor in education and training (*)	↑	↑
Tertiary education		
🕒 Tertiary educational attainment	↑	↑
🕒 Employment rate of recent graduates	↑ ⁽³⁾	↑
Adult education		
🕒 Adult participation in learning	↓	↓

(1) Multi-purpose indicator
 (2) Trend for reading performance only.
 (3) Past 6-year period.
 (*) Past 12-year period.

Table 2: Indicators measuring progress towards SDG 4, EU-28

Innovation procurement is a tool that enables **USER DRIVEN** development of innovative learning technology for a large group of buyers and joint investments. All Member States in Europe struggle with **early school leaving and under achievement in math, reading and science**. By posing the question of how can innovative technology support teachers and students to reach SDG 4 for Europe, and challenging the market directly to develop technology to meet these two specific targets, real progress can begin to be made.

Mission oriented education

https://ec.europa.eu/info/horizon-europe-next-research-and-innovation-framework-programme/missions-horizon-europe_en

In the upcoming policy and strategy work of EC (for example Horizon Europe framework program beginning 2021) the term **missions** will be used and implemented. European research and innovation missions aim to deliver solutions to some of the greatest challenges facing our world.

Characteristics of a mission-based approach to achieve results

Each mission is a mandate to solve a pressing challenge in society within a certain timeframe and budget. It focuses on **the potential of mission-oriented, strategic public sector investment to catalyse economic activity, spark innovation, solve public problems, and lay the foundations for future economic growth**.

The consensus in commentaries on mission-oriented policy today are that it has three main themes:

- A challenge-based approach
- Creation of markets
- Integration of supply and demand-side policies

In brief, missions shall have a common (public and citizens) challenge aligned with an SDG, and the result is mission projects that create new markets and fulfil the mission.

Innovation procurement is designed exactly the same way with a common societal challenge as a driving force for public sector to challenge the market to develop innovations to meet that same challenge. Innovation procurement will therefore be a strong and powerful tool to implement missions and in particular mission oriented education to achieve SDG 4 – quality in education.

Underneath LEA presents illustrations of movement from broad challenge to specific missions on a general level and one Mission created for education in relation to the SDG 4 quality in education 2030 and innovation procurement.

Figure 1 below illustrates the movement from broad challenges to specific missions.

Figure 2: Example of a mission design from EC

Figure 3: Example of mission oriented education by LEA (Ellinor Wallin 2020-06-23)

As the illustration on page 10 shows the blending of key words and trends towards 2030 enhanced by innovation procurement can create a potential CO-CREATION MISSION for education aligned with UN SDG 4 on Quality in Education.

Based upon such a future scenario, the LEA Roadmap shall provide inspiration to create similar mission oriented projects in Europe supported by the following LEA concepts presented.

- LEA – N Buyers network - a critical mass of learning technology procurers
- LEA Procurement Tool – analysis of demand and demand policy
- Country profiles – showcasing the market to companies
- Learning technology market foresight 2030
- PCP project design and recommendations
- PPI project design and recommendations
- Cross sectorial innovation procurement
- School labs and CO-CREATION
- Capacity building concepts (Online course, PR material, films)
- Exploitation Strategy 2020 and beyond, (including LEA experts and online course)
- 5 steps towards innovative co-creation models in 2030
- LEA's response to COVID-19 Crisis

It is the strong belief of LEA consortium that the findings of this Roadmap can be used to support important actions in European schools upfront.

Summing up

In brief, if schools and procurers lack understanding, experience and knowledge of innovative purchase models and procurement, digital learning can never be successful.

Increased capacity, strengthened client expertise, analysis of the schools' needs, mobilising the power of large buyers' network, co- creation including dialogue with suppliers and updates of innovative purchase and procurement methods is needed.

By using this roadmap for guidance and support, innovation procurement will be a good tool to use to inspire to innovative co-creation business models that put schools in the driving seat of Education!

3. LEA – N Buyers Network, a critical mass of learning technology buyers

LEA – N Buyers network - a critical mass of learning technology procurers

Headline	Summary of content
Challenge identified	Lack of Buyers network in education sector with a focus on accelerating uptake and pooling demand for innovative learntech
How LEA overcome the challenge and lessons learned	Creation of LEA-Network (LEA-N)
Related LEA actions to overcome Covid – 19 impact	A series of five webinars on how learning technology can support online learning
Results	As of the 30th June 2020, 72 procuring organisations have actively participated in LEA-N activities, from 16 EU Member States
Conclusions	Two-step approach to network creation is advised, given low initial awareness of the topic, and the ability to scale-up involvement accordingly. Recruitment activities can be helped through availability of clearly defined benefits.
Recommendations towards 2030	Demand for learntech by schools remains in a nascent phase. LEA-N provides a starting point for consolidating demand, and should be used as a foundation for future work in this area
Lack of dialogue between procurers and suppliers in order to understand needs and to implement new ideas for the edtech market	LEA school labs

Table 3: The lack of edtech buyers' network in the education sector

Challenge description

Before LEA, no network with a specific focus on innovation procurement in education technology existed. The existence of a network can provide practical support for procurers for doing innovation procurement, helping them to understand challenges and identify opportunities in a supportive environment. Networks can also be used to profile procurement as an important function within an organisation, building internal support at both the political and technical level.

Finally, networks form a necessary foundation for future cooperation, in particular pooling of demand and joint procurement.

How LEA overcome the challenge

LEA created the first network of public procurers who want to learn about leartech and how to buy it. It is called LEA-N. LEA-N was created in two phases:

- Collection of LEA Followers (M1 – 12)
- Formation of LEA Network (M12 – 24)

LEA Followers

As a first step, the collection of LEA Followers aimed to develop a wide pool of stakeholders – including procurers, but also suppliers, leartech experts and schools – from across Europe, to increase the visibility of procurement as an important tool for accelerating leartech. To Follow LEA was an opportunity for passive learning about the project and the topic in general.

All project partners actively recruited LEA Followers. This made use of the existing social networks of partners, who are well placed to reach relevant colleagues and peers at a national level. In addition, each partner was tasked with finding additional Followers from one or more EU Member States not covered by the project, ensuring a wide geographic spread.

In order to support partners identify and monitor their recruitment of Followers, a LEA Follower Partner Strategy was created, along with a range of communication tools (including an invitation letter, newsbit, social medial templates and sign-up form to be taken to events) outlining the benefits of following LEA.

As of June 2020, 375 people are signed up as LEA Followers, including 89 procurers, 116 suppliers, 113 schools and 125 leartech experts. Of these, 295 Followers are located in 27 EU Member States, plus 80 Followers from 21 non-EU countries.

LEA Network

In Month 12, work to embed and enlarge LEA-N began. Unlike the LEA Followers, the LEA-N only includes public procurers who actively engage in network activities (such as events and the Procurement Challenge Tool) and who are interested in collaborating in future activities.

To kick-start this work, the results of the LEA Followers recruitment activities were analysed, and a strategy for building LEA-N outlined (project deliverable 2.3). This included detailed information on success criteria, recruitment tactics, Key Performance Indicators and the minimum requirements, benefits and commitments needed to join the LEA-N.

The strategy defined responsibilities, deadlines, and targets for each partner. All partners had responsibilities to recruit members, and some strategic actions to

connect with specific initiatives or other networks were also defined. The following recruitment resources were also prepared:

- Overview of LEA-N benefits and expected contribution
- Assistance & Support request for LEA-N members
- Template Letter of Intent to be signed by potential LEA-N Members.

However, the challenge of low awareness remained. Procurers either felt they did not have the knowledge to be involved in such a network, or did not have the mandate to sign a formal Letter of Intent on behalf of their organisations. In addition, recruiting LEA-N members before key resources were available was also a challenge, as the immediate benefits of joining were not tangible.

As such, the approach was adjusted, with the emphasis being placed first and foremost on active participation in activities, such as attending a LEA Network event (described below), or participating in the Procurement Challenge Tool. It was hoped that practical activities would be more attractive to procurers as a first contact, and would raise their understanding of LEA-N and their enthusiasm for future networking.

A second challenge to overcome is the making a network devised in a 'top-down' approach from a European level, interesting to practitioners working on the ground. On 4th December at the Turin partner meeting, a workshop was held by ICLEI and EUPK on overcoming obstacles to LEA-N recruitment. One of the main barriers was language - both the general need for English language as a prerequisite for participation, but also the difference in project and practitioner terminology. As a result, an 'Easy to Read' summary called 'Why Join the LEA Network' was created, which describes the network using language proposed by the procurers themselves.

LEA-N Event

It was planned that the LEA-Network would meet in person for networking, capacity building and identifying opportunities for future collaboration. Due to the outbreak of COVID-19 and subsequent travel and meeting restrictions, the LEA-N event was reorganised as a webinar series on the topic "Procuring Resilient Education Technology".

The choice of topic was twofold. On the one hand, COVID-19 has a huge impact on schools: globally, at least 90% of the world's student population has been affected by closure of schools and universities, and any initiative on education had to reflect this current reality. On the other hand, learntech has an important role to play in managing the closure of schools and move to distance learning.

In order to replace the full day LEA-N event, it was decided that a webinar series of shorter meetings would be more effective, as engagement is difficult to maintain over a full-day online meeting. Five webinars were organised, taking place every second Wednesday at 10.30-11.30 between 15th April and 10th June. The goal was to reassess schools learntech needs in the current crisis, hearing directly from teachers how they are coping with tools currently available on the market, what

these tools can and cannot offer, how innovation procurement could help fill gaps, and how to get started on innovation procurement. Invitations to the webinar series were sent to LEA Followers, and all partners were responsible for inviting their own LEA-N contacts.

In total, 106 people from 91 organisations participated in the LEA-N webinar series, including 35 procurers (including schools, municipalities, regional governments, supportive agencies or other public sector contracting authorities) from 15 countries.

Results

As of the 30th June 2020, 72 procuring organisations have actively participated in LEA-N activities, from 16 EU Member States

Conclusions

A two-step approach to Network development was successful. Followers could sign-up to learn about the project and topic, without needing to commit further. In terms of recruiting Followers, communication templates with clearly defined benefits were helpful, as were personalised approaches from partners, who found it helpful to provide more local context when communicating with their own contacts. Through this first engagement, several Followers went on to participate in LEA-N activities.

One area for possible improvement could have been the definition of more tangible benefits for Followers and LEA-N participants. However, given the short timeframe of the project (which only ran for two years), recruitment began before output and activities were available. Future network creation initiatives could focus more on upfront value creation, developing resources early in the project which could then be used to make benefits more tangible and boost recruitment.

Recommendations towards 2030

Future projects or initiatives should focus on deepening the quality of engagement, increasing the depth of procurers' knowledge of innovation procurement, and developing more practical experiences of PPI and PCP of learntech. Tangible experiences are a valuable tool for promoting more innovation procurement procedures and the uptake of learntech more generally.

The LEA-Network has done valuable early work developing demand across Europe for learntech and raising awareness of innovation procurement as a tool in the education sector. LEA-N will be maintained, and should be used as a foundation for future work in this area

4. LEA Procurement Tool and demand towards 2030

Table with summary of concept

Headline	Summary of content
Challenge identified	High complexity of challenges in the educational system such as lack of teachers, school dropouts, challenges with technical teaching and learning aids and a missing network for innovation procurement to solve potential identified challenges.
How LEA overcome the challenge and lessons learned	Identify necessary functions for the tool, using the website of LEA to implement the tool, test the tool with the members, using LEA Members to start the network
Related LEA actions to overcome Covid – 19 impact	Not relevant
Results	Procurement Idea Tool at LEA Website
Conclusions	In the future, the Procurement Idea Tool will provide the link between the individual actors.
Recommendations towards 2030	Discussion about potential functions that could be included into the tool in the future because of that the identified challenges become more important.

Table 4: The challenges of the educational system

Challenge description

The challenges facing educational institutions, students, teachers and school administrations in the 21st century have become more complex due to the influences of today's time and society. This complexity is

- a) difficult for individual actors to grasp; and,
- b) difficult to solve.

These challenges are partly country-specific (see Deliverable 3.2) and partly they affect all schools, school types and countries. In particular, the digitisation of schools is an example of a challenge that knows no national boundaries. It is not enough to deal with the solution of challenges. First of all, challenges must be identified before solutions can be created and optimized.

In LEA are four types of experts: procurers, suppliers, technical experts and schools. Each of the experts gets a special perspective on challenges and needs through their own area. These perspectives relate not only to their own technical or professional field, but also to their country or region of origin. The combination of these different perspectives is the chance for transnational and interdisciplinary cooperation. The goal must therefore be to use the existing network to create a basis for potential innovation procurement from the available resources.

One of the major advantages of communication technology must be exploited: networking. For the identification of challenges, especially in the educational context, it is important not only to rely on one's own judgement, but to network with experts and those affected beyond national borders. So networking can immediately become a tool for solving identified challenges and questions. A possibility is sought to facilitate networking on the basis of identified challenges or solutions to be discussed. All actors should come together at the same level. Therefore, the tool has to give the answers to the following important questions:

1. Which are the needs or challenges in other countries or areas?
2. Who has identified these challenge(s) or idea(s)?
3. Who wants to join my topic? Who has more input or ideas?
4. Are there solutions or procurements I can join?

How LEA overcome the challenge

First, potential functions were searched for that the tool should provide so that the task could be fulfilled. The tool must cover the following basic areas and functions:

- Short description of the item
- Contact details
- Classification by type of the item
- Transparency for owners of the input (Who wants to join, who is interested)
- Protection of the contact details of the members who create or join an item

The first thoughts on the concept of the tool were presented to the LEA-Consortium and the procurers at the LEA meeting in Turin. In two work phases, the proposals for functions and the framework of the tool were discussed and further elaborated. The results were used to design a first template, which was checked for technical feasibility on the LEA website. From this review with the responsible technicians of the website, the actual tool has emerged.

After it has been determined in coordination with other project members and procurers that the tool should be available to LEA members, the tool is implemented in the protected LOGIN area of the website.

After the implementation of the draft version of the tool on the project website, the procurers were asked to test it. Different items should be created and shared and the visibility of existing items should be checked. A special focus was placed on the intuitive use of the tool, so that it can be ruled out in advance that the tool is not used because the application is too complex. No suggestions for improvement or optimization were made during this test phase. The tool could thus be activated on the website after the test phase and is already in use.

Results

The final version of the tool was implemented on the LEA website in collaboration with our project partner E.N.T.E.R. The focus was placed on the identified functions. At the first site of the tool it shows a list of all items and ideas. Members of LEA can join an idea and can get in touch with the creators of the idea. They can also do

some comments on the ideas. The creators of the ideas get push mails, if somebody made a comment or wants to join.

For getting in touch and joining an idea the tool has a voting function. So every member can easily vote an idea or item. The mask for the creation of a new topic or idea is very smart to use (table 1 in the following). There are 4 small steps to share an idea or identified challenge with the tool. Every user of the tool shares his or her contact details so it is very easy to get in touch with interested members or with the creators of an item.

We presented the tool at the Webinar LEA-N Webinar Series - Procuring resilient education technology and showed how to use it.

The simplified way of communication should not only simplify the beginning of potential procurement, but strengthen it. The ideas, needs and challenges presented provide a basis for discussion with the LEA community. This discussion can lead to cross-national and interdisciplinary cooperation which procurement needs to start successfully.

How to create a new item	
Step 1	Login at www.learntechaccelerator.eu use the item 'Get Involved' and choose 'LEA Procurement Idea Tool'
Step 2	<p>Here you can find three important items: Title (1); Description (2); Tags (3)</p>
Step 3	You have to find a title for your idea. The Title should name the main topic/ idea or challenge you want to publish.
Step 4	The description is very important for you and the procurers you want to find. Write the most important information about your topic.
Step 5	The Tags are your keywords. It is necessary, that you choose one or more of keywords (like education, learning technology, challenge, idea, ...) It is allowed to find some more keywords like school, lack of teacher, budget, ...
Step 6	press the submit button

Table 5: The use of the main functions of the LEA procurement tool

Conclusions

In the future, the Procurement Idea Tool will provide the link between the individual actors. It serves as a platform for exchange and inspiration.

The individual topics, challenges and ideas are freely visible to all members of the network, so that even without direct communication, an adaptation of the identified topics to one's own country or organisation is possible. Thus, it is expected that innovation procurement will be easier to start because

1. potential contents and topics are visible and a review on own topics is facilitated and
2. relevant groups of people are visible and can be contacted

The intensive and concrete exchange of content and ideas offers the potential to quickly build a network, not only to implement current ideas, but also to react to future challenges and topics.

Recommendations towards 2030

Over time, the topics and ideas submitted will be used to create a database of identified challenges and corresponding solutions or innovation procurement. In order to be able to use this collection of knowledge, data and contacts efficiently, further functions should be reviewed in the future. It is conceivable that the tool will be opened to the outside world with rudimentary information, thus not only increasing the visibility of the tool but also making it equally attractive to become part of the LEA network.

The tool was to be given a feedback function in the further course of the project, in which the ideas and items posted could be classified into three categories:

1. item open
2. item in process
3. item solved

Another potential function could be a ranking system for the items. So it would become easy to identify an idea or challenge what is marked as very important for innovation procurement.

5. LEA country profiles

Table with summary of concept

Headline	Summary of content
Challenge identified	Lack of information about the procurement procedures of each EU Member State and about the

	<p>details of the demand side of learning technology procurement.</p> <p>Innovation procurement is not a widespread way of buying learning technologies, though it can make education more effective</p>
How LEA overcome the challenge and lessons learned	LEA has analysed the procurement arena of the EU Member States and made the result visible for suppliers by publishing country profile cards
Results	Learntech Accelerator Procurement Analysis and 28 Country profile cards
Conclusions	The education system, decision-making process and public procurement procedures are different in the different countries of the EU and in the United Kingdom. The country profile cards give country specific information, increase the knowledge of suppliers and help to align the demand and supply side as well as to inspire and launch innovation procurement in education
Recommendations towards 2030	The spread of information related to innovation procurement, the support of cooperation networks, such as LEA-N for implementing common innovation procurement related to learning technology and ensuring its financial source are essential to help the global aims determined to develop education to be achieved

Table 6: Lack of information about EU procurement procedures

Challenge description

Suppliers do not have exact information about the demand side of the European learning technology market. The supply side (SMEs, start-ups) industry and R&I institutes risk facing the “valley of death” to get a commercial product on the market. The industry in general lacks a deeper understanding of demand / user needs aligned with the societal challenges of the public sector. Apart from the needs of the end users, they need to know:

- who the buyers are, how big the market is;
- who the actors of education in each country are and what their role is;
- which organisations are responsible for the procurement of learning technologies;
- who the decision-makers are;
- what the steps of the procurement procedures are;
- what kind of legal regulations and other rules the procurers have to follow to implement a procurement;
- how much money they have to implement developments in education and to buy learning technologies etc.

It was essential to enable a better mutual understanding between the end users, the procurers and the suppliers that can facilitate innovative procurement in education.

Innovative procurement is not so well-known and widespread in Europe related to education, though it can contribute to making education more effective and fitted to real needs, so it was also a challenge to empower the LEARNTECH ecosystem stakeholders by knowledge transfer in order to remove barriers of innovative procurement.

How LEA overcome the challenge

LEA identified the procurement arena of Education in Europe in order to map levels of procurement in different countries and barriers of legislation standards, as well as the main challenges faced by the public sector. The information contributed to the effective work with the demand policies and innovative procurement on EU level.

To gain information, we analysed white papers and reports. Desk research was an effective method to collect information as there are official documents, reports and statistics made for the European Union and the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). These reports summarize different sectors and their structure in each country. From these documents much information could be utilised to map the education technology procurement system in the countries. These documents could be downloaded free of charge; thus, the research was based on cost-effectively obtained reliable and relevant data.

The secondary data sources were completed with primary data collection through the information provided by the organisations participating in the LEA project. A questionnaire was also conducted by INNOVA and filled out by LEA partners. This improved the information content of the report, as the organisations gathered data not only from publicly available sources, but on the basis of their own practice and experience as well. Among the partners, there are municipalities that are involved in the public procurement processes of ICT tools in their area. Thus, they were able to describe different points of view: the users' point of view, the decision-makers' point of view, the point of view of an authority.

A questionnaire was used as a structured technique for collecting primary data from LEA partner countries. It was generally a series of written questions for which respondents had to provide answers. The option for online questionnaire was used due to different locations of the respondents for the purpose that the data would be more convenient and faster to collect. The questionnaire provided a systematic way to analyse the information. Some descriptive statistical information and figures about the respondents' characteristics were included in the analysis.

The main goal was to prepare an accurate, well-designed questionnaire in order to motivate the respondents to give relevant and complete information. The questions have been edited to not have a manipulative impact on the answers. In this way, reliable information had been obtained from the respondents.

Open-ended questions were used in the case of the indication of the decision-making organisations for ICT procurement, because every country is different, and there are types of organisations which are only relevant and valid for only one

country, thus, we were not able to predict the answer possibilities. In all the cases when it was possible to indicate the possible answers from previous experience or knowledge about the partner/country, close-ended questions were used with multiple answer possibilities. There were some closed-ended questions used with two possible opposite outcomes (e.g. *Do the primary/secondary schools have the right to decide what kind of educational technology tool to purchase?*). However, in this type of question, a plus option was also given (*other*) to provide the opportunity to express that the respondent does not have enough information to provide an answer. This was necessary in order to prevent the distortion of the result and get invalid results. Answers were only acceptable if the respondents specified what the “other” option exactly covered.

Moreover, in case of all questions and answers, space for comments was provided to give the possibility to add explanations and further information in connection with the answer.

Ranking questions were also used: in one question respondents were asked to indicate the importance of listed factors. The indication was between 1-not important at all and 4-extremely important. In the case of all factors only one answer could be chosen, however, it was possible to add further factors and indicate their importance. The question was about the decisive factors in the choice of education technology tools, and the list of factors which were compiled based on experience from the IMAILE project.

A questionnaire has been created in order to obtain more detailed information about the situation regarding public procurement of ICT solutions in education in all the LEA partners' countries: Austria, Finland, Germany, Hungary, Portugal, Spain and Sweden. Altogether 20 organisations provided responses to the questions.

Results

On the basis of the information collected during the identification of the procurement arena of Education in Europe, **D3.1. Learntech Accelerator Procurement Analysis** was compiled. The analysis gives information about learning technology procurement in the countries of the European Union and the United Kingdom, maps learntech procurers as first buyers and identifies the barriers of the demand side as well. The education government system of the countries was analysed, while the decision-making processes and parties taking part in the decision making were also described. Thanks to this analysis, LEA Consortium has deeper knowledge about the levels of procurement in the different countries and the barriers of legislation standards in Austria, Belgium, Finland, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Portugal, Spain and Sweden. It can be used to understand how to use the LEA Network with a broader approach and it could be used to prepare the PPI. The analysis can be used as business case for suppliers defining target market and customer segmentation.

As it is beneficial to see demand policy, money and procurement information per country for the suppliers, we have prepared country profile cards which summarized information sorted to the following chapters for each Member State of

the European Union and the United Kingdom to make the result of the research and the conclusions of the analysis more visible for suppliers:

- Numbers (of schools, classes, classrooms, students, teachers, students per computer)
- Legislation of education
- Organisations participating in the system of education
- Funding of education
- Public expenditure on education
- Expenditure on educational institutions
- Investment plan for education / ICT in education
- Procurement procedure
- Other important information

The analysis and the country profile cards can contribute to the increased knowledge of suppliers. These outputs gather customers of Learning Technology in Europe and make them visible to the industry, so they can align demand and supply side and enforce LEA-N Network as well. The forms are published on the LEA website: <https://www.learntechaccelerator.eu/procurement-in-europe/>

Conclusions

It can be stated that all the Member States have different systems regarding the governance and authority of the system of educational institutions. With the help of the analysis, we were able to draw a general picture of the present situation of the above-mentioned system in the European Union. We could also come into conclusions regarding the decisive factors in procurement decisions and the authorities and rights in the respective countries.

Hence the considerable differences according to the dimension of the level of centralization, we can classify the countries into two groups: centralized and decentralized countries. The table below shows the classification:

Centralized	Decentralized
Austria	Cyprus
Belgium	Czech Republic
Bulgaria	Estonia
Croatia	Finland
Denmark	Latvia
France	Malta
Germany	Poland
Greece	Slovakia
Hungary	Slovenia
Ireland	Spain
Italy	Sweden
Lithuania	
Luxembourg	
The Netherlands	
Portugal	
Romania	
United Kingdom	

Table 7: The level of centralization in different countries

The classification was made on the basis of the decision-making rights in the education system taking into consideration the effect of the schools' opinion on the procurement. Even within a country there could be differences in the decisive factors and the decision-making system regarding educational technology tool public procurements. However, most of the respondents consider price as one of the most important factors that are taken into consideration, but the average of the classification does not show considerable differences between the importance of factors.

It also became clear that innovation procurement methods and procedures are still not common in the Member States of the European Union and in the United Kingdom.

Recommendations towards 2030

Innovation procurement related to education technology tools is not so widespread in the Member States of the European Union, but there is a need from the side of procurers to know more about that, it is necessary to spread all information about the methodology, risks and advantages, steps of the innovation procurement process, etc. Cooperation networks such as LEA-N need to be supported and further strengthened to help link the demand and supply side of the market, and help procurers implementing common innovation procurements related to purchasing learning technologies, as it can contribute to achieving objectives such as increasing the effectiveness of education through teaching methods and tools which are appropriate for real needs. The development of education in this way can also contribute to the spread of digital education and the reduced number of early school leavers. The other important issue related to innovation procurement is the funding. The financial background of such development needs to be established.

6. Learning technology market foresight 2030

Headline	Summary of content
Challenge identified	Which learning technologies to invest in - learning technology market foresight for 2030
How LEA overcome the challenge and lessons learned	In order to overcome challenge "which learning technologies to invest in", we organized series of events: global thinkthank at BETT2019, external capacity building

	<p>seminar at INTED2019 and 11 webinars. Focus group discussions were also held in 7 countries (LEA School labs) where future needs were explored, discussed and visioned with headmasters, teachers, students and policy makers.</p> <p>These actions helped us to shape our understanding of the state-of-the-art of the technologies and future needs relevant to procurement organizations</p>
Related LEA actions to overcome Covid – 19 impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Webinars instead of live-events: 15.4. 2020: Tales from teachers – how has or could technology help in this current crisis? • Facebook group: https://www.facebook.com/groups/518115792458297/ • Curated YouTube Channel (curated by project member Jari Laru): www.youtube.com/jarilaru
Results	<p>11 webinars, 1 global thinkthank event, 1 external capacity building seminar (where 7 conference presentations with abstracts) and related project deliverables. LEA Market foresight is presented in D4.3. Report on future global market of Learntech 2030 as well as in various webinars to the field.</p>
Conclusions	<p>LEA project has organised many different events for procurers, schools, teachers and other stakeholders about the current and future trends of the learning technologies. Recorded webinars, publications and online course together will help to understand what the market foresight for 2030.</p>
Recommendations towards 2030	<p>In the near future (ten years ahead) educational technologies will be disrupted by the new interface and background technologies. In the following listing you will get a brief glimpse of the technologies which will rapidly come into mainstream and therefore need to be taken into account also in the procurement process.</p>

Table 8: Choosing which learning technology to invest in

Challenge description

In general, the level of capacity and experience in innovative technology is low among the majority of schools and municipalities in Europe. In addition, the edtech market itself is still evolving, allowing rapid fluctuations in the range of products that are available for the buyers. This makes it hard to take the right decision on which learning technologies to invest in and why. In many cases, schools and municipalities invest in the same digital products and services as their "neighbours" do. However, the decision to invest in edtech should be based on the actual needs and capabilities of the school or municipality in question, including different

aspects such as affordability, continuity of use and pedagogical validity. To support the buyers of digital learning, LEA has gathered several analyses using a variety of tools both as public project deliverables to the European Commission and to the education community.

How LEA overcome the challenge

LEA has taken action to better understand the market foresight towards 2030. This includes the compilation of public reports, such as **D3.2 Requirements for Professional Teacher Training** and **D4.1 State of the Art Analysis**. The topic has also been covered by experts in many episodes of the LEA webinar series that discuss, for example, the learntech market, computational thinking in schools, AI (artificial intelligence) in education and using analytics to change the assessment culture in schools. The complete list of the webinars can be found in the [LEA website](#). In addition, the LEA project hosted a global Think Tank event for edtech suppliers at the 2019 Bett Show. Topics discussed included innovation procurement and related funding opportunities for the suppliers, predicting the future of edtech 2030 (slides available in [SlideShare](#)), and envisioning future technologies for education workshop with both LEA procurers and suppliers.

An external capacity building seminar gave LEA consortium members the chance to disseminate their ideas to the seminar audience. As a result, altogether seven papers were presented in the INTED2019 seminar (*13th International Technology, Education and Development Conference*), the abstracts of which are also available in the seminar proceedings. The topics discussed in the papers include making cost effective and sustainable decisions regarding future technology in schools and municipalities, tools to steer the market towards innovative solutions for education as well as the relationship between emergent technology and future learning and teaching. Finally, emergent learning technologies are discussed in a bonus chapter of the LEA Online Course, which is available through the [LEA website](#) for the LEA-Network members

Results

11 webinars, 1 global thinkthank event, 1 external capacity building seminar (where 7 conference presentations with abstracts) and related project deliverables.

Conclusions

LEA project has organised many different events for procurers, schools, teachers and other stakeholders about the current and future trends of learning technologies. Recorded webinars, publications and online course together will help to understand what the market foresight for 2030.

Recommendations towards 2030

In the near future (ten years ahead) educational technologies will be disrupted by the new interface and background technologies. In the following listing you will get a brief glimpse of the technologies which will rapidly come into mainstream and therefore needs to be taken into account also in procurements processes.

Artificial Intelligence: The rapid development of artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms and therewith personalised learning environments (PLEs) has the ability to deepen, enrich and adaptively learn and interact. AI is utilised in two main ways in learning environments. It can help in assessment of the learning process and give timely feedback of student's learning performance to both students themselves and their teachers through different dashboards and support tools. Another way to utilise AI in PLEs is in the form of personal learning assistants such as conversational agents able to communicate either with spoken or written language.

Learning Analytics: Students leave digital traces while they are using different learning technologies which can be captured and analysed and therefore develop recommendations to facilitate learning. So, in practice, learning analytics can provide personalised and timely correct feedback to each student.'

Extended Reality: In literature, virtual realities are traditionally described as technological systems accompanied by gear such as head-mounted displays to enable immersive experiences. Augmented reality, in turn, can be used to describe systems attempting to combine virtual elements with real-life settings. It could be stated that while at its best, virtual reality is something that the user is cast into, augmented realities brings certain aspects of the virtual world to be a part of the user's everyday environment. In the close future, technological development will bring real and virtual environments closer to one another. In this sense, XR technologies might become normal parts of people's everyday lives, making it possible to integrate educational activities into environments which are natural and meaningful for learners.

Games and Gamification: The use of digital games for learning started to gain research attention at the turn of the century, making it a fairly new phenomenon in the field of education. Games themselves are quite normal educational tools, digital drill-and-practise games are quite typical in many levels of the education, but also open-ended games are increasingly used in schools, such as Minecraft Education Edition. However, it has been noticed that certain elements used in popular games seem to appeal to several people. These include e.g. the use of leader boards and collecting badges based on achievements, which is called "gamification". Reasons to play games can include enjoyment, but also feelings of success, competence or achievement. Social aspects of gaming should not be forgotten. It is possible that in the future games and gamification are used as a natural part of learning, since playing digital games is an essential part of the contemporary life of younger generations.

Pedagogical Agents: Pedagogical agents (PA) are characters which are intended to facilitate learning. PAs appear in digital learning environments to help students and can have physical appearance such as a robot. Educational specialists have forecasted that teachers will be assisted by machine agents such as social robots and virtual tutors within the next 10 years. The main feature is their ability to communicate with students as they are communicational agents utilising artificial intelligence. Their strength is that they can take multiple roles depending of the

needs of a student. These roles can be for example peer, competitor, teacher or learning assistant.

Robotics: In recent years, robotics has been a popular topic especially in the field of STEAM (science, technology, engineering, arts, and mathematics) education. Use of robotics to design and model situations and elements with different levels of complexity has been perceived as a potential channel to enhance students' creativity and autonomous work. Even though it might not be probable or meaningful to use robotics in education to replace teachers, in some scenarios use of robotics might bring education closer to students, making it more personal and tactile.

Blockchain technology: Blockchain could offer solutions for ensuring the security of exchanging learning information between ecosystems, institutions and other stakeholders.

Wearable technology: Years of research in the field of psychophysiology has confirmed that our cognition is not separate from the body, instead many mental states are reflected through physiological signals. It is quite clear that wearables in the future could become functional gadgets in the learning ecosystem, because these can provide information of the learning processes.

Making and digital fabrication: Making (Makerspaces) is a central concept in the maker education approach. In practice, making is "a class of activities focused on designing, building, modifying, and/or repurposing material objects, for playing or useful ends, oriented toward making a 'product' that can be used, interact with, or demonstrated" (Martin, 2015, p. 31). In the context of digital fabrication (making) and fabrication laboratories (fab labs), complex, undefined, open-ended, and unstructured problem-solving activities are typical (Chan & Blikstein, 2018).

7. The COVID-19 Crisis

Headline	Summary of content
Challenge identified	Spring 2020 brought a new challenge to all the schools all over the world: The effects of the COVID-19 crisis on how education is organized
How LEA overcome the challenge and lessons learned	In order to overcome the challenge, LEA has provided support in different ways, including <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Setting up Facebook group for sharing good practices among teachers (530 members)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • support for schools, for example in the form of consultation (LEA expert panel work) • teacher interviews in the LEA webinar series • presentations in online conferences • setting up a serie of webinars where teachers could connect and share their experiences as well as to receive support • In addition, LEA expert Jari Laru curated youtube videos which can help teachers during the covid-19 crisis. <p>These actions helped us to share our knowledge regarding the use of technology in teaching, gain a deeper understanding of the effects that the COVID-19 crisis has had on practitioners' daily teaching practices as well as to disseminate the work done by the LEA project.</p>
Related LEA actions to overcome Covid – 19 impact	The actions have been taken with particular consideration to the COVID-19 crisis. In addition, the conferences that LEA participated in have been delivered online, while yhe Facebook group was chosen as a platform due to its familiarity and good availability to teachers worldwide.
Results	Three presentations given in three online conferences, one paper waiting for final publication, teacher interviews in LEA webinar series
Conclusions	LEA project has answered to the need rising from schools in providing different kinds of information and support for schools and teachers during the COVID-19 crisis.
Recommendations towards 2030	The COVID-19 crisis has created a rapid shift in how education is organized for learners. It is important to keep up with the developments of the situation, as it might further shape the future of the use of learning technology in education. LEA Network can be utilised also in the future to support schools when going back to the classrooms in the Autumn.

Challenge Description

The COVID-19 crisis put many teachers worldwide in a situation where they need to organize distance education to their learners. In many cases, the shift has been very rapid, as schools have been forced to close their doors in order to slow the spread of the virus. It has been popular to organize distance education with the help of new technology, such as different videoconferencing software and learning management systems (LMSs). However, it should be noted that teachers and schools have very different capabilities in organizing online education, including knowledge of how to different technologies in education.

Many countries have responded to the COVID-19 situation by investing into network connections, laptops and remodelling of their school spaces within a very fast schedule in Spring-Summer 2020. This means there is a need for LEA network

help to share experiences in buying effective and useful technologies for the schools. LEA will follow this up in the webinars in Autumn 2020.

How LEA overcome the challenge

The LEA project noticed very quickly that support was needed to provide distance education to learners. In order to help teachers to learn about new technologies available and promote sharing of good practices among the practitioners, LEA created the Facebook group [Organizing teaching during COVID-19 crisis](#). The group is also used for research purposes, in order to gain a deeper understanding of the ways in which the COVID-19 crisis has affected the education practices. LEA members have also provided support for schools in the spring, for example in the form of consultation in Italy. In addition, teachers have been interviewed for the LEA webinar series.

Related to the COVID-19 situation, LEA has presented one paper in the *EdMedia + Innovate Learning 2020 Online* conference (23-26/6/2020), which will be published in the conference proceedings.

Mäkelä, T., Mehtälä, S., Clements, K. & Seppä, J. (2020). Schools Went Online Over One Weekend - Opportunities and Challenges for Online Education Related to COVID-19 Crisis. Proceedings of EdMedia + Innovate Learning 2020 Online Conference

The abstract of the paper is available at [AcademicExperts.org](#). Related to organizing teaching during the COVID-19 crisis, members of LEA have also been speaking in different events, including JYU UNESCO-CCE [Online Conference: Embrace the Creativity amidst COVID-19 Crisis](#) by CCE-Finland (21/4/2020) and the *Challenges of Online Teaching and Learning Virtual Conference*, organized by Khazar University (6/5/2020).

Results

Facebook group for sharing good practices among teachers, three presentations in three online conferences, one paper published in EdMedia 2020 conference. In addition, LEA expert Jari Laru curated youtube videos which can help teachers during the covid-19 crisis. Find the playlist here: <https://www.youtube.com/jarilaru>

Conclusions

The COVID-19 crisis has changed the ways in which education is provided for learner worldwide, and the LEA project has been active in providing information and support during this crisis. The participation of different stakeholders is crucial, in order to ease the formation of technology-enhanced, educational practices as well as the continuity of their use. It should also be kept in mind that the COVID-19 situation is not over and, for example, the practices for returning to school in fall need to be carefully considered.

Recommendations towards 2030

The COVID-19 crisis can have extensive effects on how education is organized in the future. Because of this, it is essential to keep up with how the crisis develops, and finally, unfolds. In the future, crisis situations such as the COVID-19 should also be included in the risk management plans.

8. Best practice PCP project design

Table with summary of the concept

Headline	Summary of content
Challenge identified	Lack of understanding and knowledge on PCP procedures
How LEA overcome the challenge and lessons learned	LEA performed various tasks that can feed a PCP process: - Needs analysis; - Market State of the art assessment; - Production of PCP ITT guidelines.
Related LEA actions to overcome Covid – 19 impact	Webinars, LEA procurement tool for joint needs , LEA online training course, Free of charge LEA PCP experts
Results	One complete PCP pre-study including business case
Conclusions	The enhancement of performance of public services, as well as the increasing long-term public expenditure effectiveness and efficiency, can be achieved by cooperation within the demand side with key involvement of need owners
Recommendations towards 2030	Be clear with the time for preparations; early involvement of the extended network of procurers; innovation needs identified; adequate language used for the different targets.

Table 9: Lack of understanding regarding PCP procedures

Challenge description

PCP is a strong tool to steer the market based upon mid to long term needs and challenges. Yet, there is still a lack of understanding and knowledge about competition rules governing the PCP procedures and the State Aid Framework. PCP concerns a competition, its various phases and specific rules, and documentation is still not adequately metabolized. The various public procurement laws and rules and their required documents might put-off potentially interested parties, especially if we are referring to a lesser well-known procedure, as it is still the case with PCP. As general evidence and challenge detected across EU

shows, the public sector has not fully metabolized and has strongly underestimated that innovation procurement is not about industrial policy.

How LEA overcome the challenge

LEA projects builds on lessons learned from IMAILE www.imaile.eu, Europe's first PCP in Education 2014 – 2018. This project has gathered several methods and templates that can be used by schools and procurers of digital learning. The following PCP methodology is recommended by IMAILE and was used in LEA:

PHASES	EXPECTED TIME LINE
PREPARATION	Total 15 months
NEED ANALYSIS, PIN AND MARKET CONSULTATION, PCP (ITT) DOCUMENTATION	11 months
OPEN CALL ON TED	4 months
EVALUATION OF FIRST BIDS	1 month
STANDSTILL PERIOD TO PREPARE CONTRACTS	1 month
PCP AND R&D PROCESS	Total 27 months
PHASE 1 DEVELOPMENT OF CONCEPT AND EVALUATION OF PHASE REPORT AND OUTPUT	4 + 1 months
PHASE 2 PROTOTYPES AND EVALUATION OF PHASE REPORT AND OUTPUT	8+14 + 1 months
PHASE 3 TEST PHASE 3 TEST	12+1
GATHER RESULTS TOWARDS KPIS	Total 2 months
EVALUATION OF FINAL INNOVATIONS, ANALYSIS AND GATHER RESULTS	
	Total PCP project 44 months

Table 10: PCP Methodology and benchmark on timeline

LEA PCP preparations on transversal skills Business case

A PCP shall be based upon an identified need by many procurers and schools and described as overall challenge, societal challenge, pedagogical challenge, technical and financial challenge. Underneath follows the business case that a working group in LEA prepared in 2019.

Background

Robotics, automation and AI will likely take over many future careers, hence European education should initiate to have focus on collaboration and creativity which are skills that are human related and difficult to replace by technology and machines (e.g. transversal skills) (Atenas & Havemann, 2015);. This will be one important path in order to prepare students better for future jobs and an international, dynamic and complex labour market. How can teachers teach skills they were not on focus during their teacher training? UNESCO (2015) Defines transversal skills as "Critical and innovative thinking, inter-personal skills; intra-personal skills, and global citizenship".

SEAMLESS Overall challenge

Develop innovative learning technology to meet an increased demand of

teaching and learning **transversal skills** to better prepare the next generation of Europeans for future jobs and careers unknown today. Our target group will be secondary education but potentially to use and enlarge for the future the innovative solutions to students from 6 -18. The overall PCP challenge is complex and hence it is divided into several sub challenges where different business cases and beneficial scenarios will be developed: societal, pedagogical, technical and financial challenges.

SEAMLESS Societal challenge

Prepare next generation European citizens for jobs and careers that don't exist today and an international, dynamic and complex labour market

SEAMLESS Pedagogical challenges

1. **Supporting teachers to teach transversal skills** - Support for teachers to simplify recognition, validation and teaching of transversal skills in the existing curriculum (create a pilot case)
2. **Supporting students towards increased learning of transversal skills** for future learning outcomes, careers and jobs (create a case)
3. **Supporting automatic measuring and recognizing of learning transversal skills** preparing possible drop outs early to be better prepared in life (include a cost case of early drop outs)

SEAMLESS Technical challenges demanding sustainability

- Reuse of digital devices in the classroom
- SEAMLESS solution should work on the current LMS/PLE solutions within the classroom (schools do not have a need for another platform, but a seamless experience with the current ones)
- Rechargeable technology by kinetic energy produced during sport class and or recreation
- Seamless experience using Blockchains together with AI
- Recognition of students learning transversal skills through informal channels (e.g. measuring learning through wearable devices, IoT etc.)
- Automated and self-instructive support (AI and measuring learning)
- Safe sharing of learning outcomes certificates, materials, tests and badges within European schools

SEAMLESS Financial challenges

- Costs of dropouts: how could these decrease if drop outs will be able to manage new jobs upon transversal skills instead of traditional curricula measurements;
- Decreasing the costs of training teachers;
- Educating students to be flexible and skilled to adapt to the need of the labour market (decreasing so-called 'Life drop-outs' later in life)

Based upon this challenge the following business case was created to create return on investment for the potential buyers group:

SEAMLESS	Return of investment (ROI)	Suggested measurement
-----------------	-----------------------------------	------------------------------

BUSINESS CASES		methodology
10% Decrease youth unemployment	Cost of youth unemployment 2016 Greece 5684.82 M € Spain 38356.58 M € Portugal 4099.04 M € Finland 5607.53 M €	Follow students' progress after last year of secondary school, compare to average use of social benefits per country <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drop of months unemployed • Less welfare raised • Lower social costs
10% Decrease youth social exclusion	<p>Finland Case example: In Finland, one young person 'Dropped from the system' costs approximately €70 000 per year</p> <p>Savings would bring €7 000 per person (including taxes, social benefits, unemployment fee etc.)</p> <p>With 65 000 persons of age 15-24 unemployed, the savings for Finland potentially €455 000 per year with only a 10% improvement</p> <p>One 'Life drop-out' costs approximately 1,2M € over their lifetime, which would make long term ROI rather high</p>	Interviews/survey of young persons with strong transversal skills

Table 11: SEAMLESS business cases

The business cases are important to highlight to engage the procurers in the PCP investments.

LEA PCP process

To contribute to clarification and bring stakeholders closer to PCP procedures, making them more comfortable to take part in this type of processes, LEA prepared the soil for future PCP processes, by implementing the following tasks:

- Needs analysis, involving LEA procurers partners
- State of the art assessment and market scanning:

- Production of PCP ITT guidelines: this document¹ addresses the PCP and focuses on one of the steps of "Phase 0", gathering useful information and guidelines to prepare a PCP Invitation to Tenders (ITT) / Request for Tender. The ITT presents the legal framework of a PCP, containing all the relevant and necessary information concerning the PCP (description of the services to be procured, available budget, timeline, conditions, etc.).
- Search for Funding for PCP:
- PCP pre-study: a PCP working group was created with LEA procurers and other European procurers, with the goal to prepare the ground to initiate and launch innovative procurement calls of PCP/PPI.
- Open and free-of-charge assistance offered to all interested parties on PCP strategy and execution.
- Dedicated webinars where all interested participants have posed relevant questions to LEA PCP expert, namely Sara Bedin.

Results

The results have been presented in several public deliverables and reports such as one analysis of LEARNTECH procurement EU level/country & Identification of barriers to the demand-side submitted and presented on the LEA website. The analysis was based on the answers from a total 520 teachers in more than 10 countries and 1045 students in 7 countries. One business cases scenario focusing on PLE/STEM challenges and other educational challenges. One PCP invitation to tender and support. One PCP pre-study completed, info displayed on LEA web to suppliers. Presentation of innovation partnership from Vinnova (SE) and MoE France and a dedicated webinar and free-of-charge on-line assistance is also offered.

Conclusions

LEA contributed to clarifying that the leverage of public procurement as a vehicle for innovation is rooted in the recognition that today's education system almost certainly gives rise to complex needs (mainly in terms of sustainability and interoperability), whose fulfilment may not be viable merely by purchasing particular goods or services "off the shelf" and/or without a strategic vision and plan (and hopefully cross-border) aggregation of the demand, which is fundamental to assure the ground for real interoperability and interchangeability and prevention of expensive lock-in situations.

LEA has manifested and promoted that the enhancement of performance of public services, as well as the increasing long-term public expenditure effectiveness and efficiency, can be achieved by cooperation within the demand side with key involvement of need owners.

Recommendations towards 2030

The robustness and credibility of an innovation procurement is based on an action promoted by the various actors entitled to provide educational services. In other terms, the procurement has to be governed, performed and driven by a subject that has the real requirement that the innovative solutions should fulfil and related competencies, skills and therefore that KNOWS the public sector of reference.

Considering the preparation of a cross-border call for funding.

- Be clear with the time for preparations: to get commitment and understanding from procurers a pre-study needs a minimum of 3 months and shall include a minimum one meeting to discuss, plan and organise this complex process.
- Enlarge the time to work on the proposal and to work with the procurers, to have a more participative process.
- Assure a revision and internal approval process.
- Stimulate the demand aggregation through early involvement of the extended network of procurers, able to represent the market (demand-side).
- Assure that the innovation needs identified are connected to measurable KPIs.
- The needs elicitation have to be based on a specific analysis of shortcomings in the use of state-of-the-art technologies.
- Estimate an adjusted time and person-efforts to elaborate ITT documentation. Before drafting ITT documentation, it is important to have designed the whole phased PCP process, including all deliverables and templates required, authorization path and testing protocols, as well as the rights and obligations of all parties.
- Assure a sustainable schedule and a commitment to administrative tasks to avoid delays and stop-and-go which afflict the innovation developments and exploitation.
- Produce "easy to read" documents, with adjusted design - as ITT aggregate various information, a good design may help the reading and stimulate the stakeholder's interest in the PCP documentation.
- Adequate the language used to the different targets. For instance, when conducting a need analysis with the end-users, adjust the language to guarantee they will understand your aims, besides considering the necessity of translating documents.

9. Best practice PPI project design

Headline	Summary of content
Challenge identified	Lack of understanding and knowledge on PPI procedures
How LEA overcome the challenge and lessons learned	LEA performed various tasks that can feed a PPI process: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Needs analysis; - State of the art of the market; - Production of PPI ITT guidelines; - Funding for a future PPI.
Related LEA actions to overcome Covid – 19 impact	Webinars, LEA procurement tool for joint needs , LEA online training course , Free of charge LEA PCP experts
Results	One complete PPI methodology for education, PPI legal documents templates, PPI business case, published Prior Information and stakeholder dialogue
Conclusions	Ensure sufficient time and ask for legal support to make the correct decisions on how to launch the PPI call (coordinated or joint PPI call)
Recommendations towards 2030	Ensure a timeline adequate to facilitate the involvement of schools; adjust the language used for the different targets; make sure to have funding for Open Market Consultation; clearly identify needs; guarantee a clear pre-understanding of the role of a PIN for all procurers; provide enough time to evaluate the PIN.

Table 12: Lack of understanding regarding PPI procedures

Challenge description

Barriers to innovation procurement, arising both from demand and supply side, are mainly related to the fact that innovative PCP and PPI methods demand new mindsets, skills and resources (both for public procurers and for suppliers) when compared to traditional procurement approaches. Based on the experience and lessons learned from the IMAILE project, the LEA consortium will empower a network of procurers to use more efficiently these procurement tools, contributing to increasing awareness for PCP and PPI while demystifying misleading concepts around these methodological approaches and showcasing examples of success.

How LEA overcome the challenge

To contribute to clarification and bring stakeholders closer to PPI procedures, making them more comfortable to take part in this type of processes, LEA prepared the soil for future PPI processes. A PPI shall follow two steps 1) Preparatory stage and 2) Executive stage (including deployment). LEA prepared the PPI using the following methodology:

LEA innovative PPI methodology and benchmark of timeline

1. WHY and NEEDS
2. Market analysis
3. Preparations of PPI (tender documentation)
4. PPI test plan
5. PPI implementation
6. Purchase and deployment of innovative solutions

PPI timetable	Time-line
WHY and needs	6 months
Market analysis	6 months
Legal preparations	3 months
Preparations total	Up to 15 Months
Open tender period	2 months
Evaluation of bids and simultaneously offering of conformance test in school labs. One supplier per lot awarded.	3 months
Decision note of awarded systems	
Tender and awarding period total	6 months
Installation and deployment	9 – 12 months
Purchase	3 months
After sales support and evaluation, bugs fixing in schools	4 months
PPI implementation total in schools with standstill for school vacation	Up to 20 months
Total time PPI process	36 – 42 months

Table 13: PPI methodology and benchmark of timeline

1. WHY and needs

The content agreed needs and preparatory work of the needs analysis is presented in section 1 of this report. Below follows a summary of technological and functional criteria.

An intuitive, smart and easy to use PLE system for primary, secondary and upper secondary including features that:

- Measures learning (AI, learning analytics)
- Supports teachers to reduce time on planning and administration
- Supports each student to reach and control their own learning goals based

- upon creativity
 - Provides peer support/matching on an EU level for teachers
 - Provides detection, alerts and contingency on early dropouts
- Functional criteria/ self-validation by suppliers to be provided in the bids
- User cases with gained benefits of their solutions
 - Easy to use guarantee
 - Cross sectorial collaboration (Open Innovation) encouraged between suppliers to use existing technology on the market but in other fields
 - Return on investments (Business case)

Market analysis

To identify the actual personal learning solutions of the market a desktop study and interviews with the industry was performed (see section Market foresight).

Legal and funding preparations

To support the procurers and buyers group of the PPI (Konnevesi, Finland; Turin, Italy; and Braga, Portugal) ready to invest 1 million euro of their own spending and to make an financial attractive call to the market the PPI needed to be supported by additional funding. A funding report on upcoming innovation procurement processes was submitted to EC on October 2018 (D2.2) based upon which the PPI pre-study was outlined. A LEA PPI preparation workforce was created with the focus to prepare the PPI preparations towards December 2018. In parallel with this work, the preparations of the legal aspects were implemented. The PPI can be implemented using one of the following approaches: Joint PPI or Coordinated PPI. To simplify the process for the PPI procurers a pre-decision in Braga Nov 2018 of the procurers made as preparatory action in LEA was to manage the process as a Coordinated PPI Procurement approach. Coordinated PPI procurement is when the procuring partners together carry out the preparations. In coordinated actions, they explore the needs and define the common requirements specification, exchange experiences and consult the market together. Finally, each procuring partner launches its own call for tender under its respective national legislation.

Verification of PPI

For conformance tests of the PLEs asked for in the PPI, the following LEA school labs (task 2. 3) were prepared and announced in the PIN;

- Konnevesi, LEA school lab: Sep – Nov 2019
- Braga, LEA school lab: Sep – Nov 2019
- Turin, LEA school lab: Sep – Nov 2019

The PPI test plan was well described in the PPI pre-study;

Installation, deployment, coordination, conformance tests: Some conformance tests will be offered already in LEA during the Open Market Consultation to verify the PLE systems towards the PPI contract. During the award period, additional conformance tests will be offered to validate the PLE systems and determine if they comply with the technical requirements,

functional criteria, [specifications](#) and PPI contracts. Conformance testing will be performed in 'School Labs' (prepared as real classrooms but still working as labs). These labs have been prepared in LEA specific for this use.

Results

The PPI preparations made in LEA have been wrapped up as a complete PPI pre-study in education, one analysis of LEARNTECH procurement at EU level to identify the barriers on demand side, one PPI methodology for learning technology, a collection of tender documentation PIN and OMC published on TED and LEA web, and a visualised film concept in brief to share with the community.

One PIN was published on TED to announce the OMC of innovative personal learning technology and the OMC is open on LEA web and LEA partners have assisted more than 25 different EU events as speakers or exhibitors to share experiences on innovation procurement in learning technology.

Recommendations towards 2030

- Ensure a timeline adequate to facilitate the involvement of schools. PPI/PCP in education relies on cooperation with schools, therefore the timetable of the schools is essential and they differ between European countries.
- Use adequate language to describe the different targets. For instance, when conducting a need analysis with the end-users, adjust the language to guarantee they will understand your aims, besides considering the necessity of translating documents. The use of online surveys facilitated the collection of answers from teachers and students in the case of LEA, as online surveys allow people to answer when they are available.
- Time, time and time again, the common knowledge about PPI is limited
- Make sure to have funding for the OMC and how to proceed with the purchase after the OMC to attract more industrial stakeholders to receive their important input to the needs and development of technology.
- Make sure to have clearly identified needs, as it is the baseline of all innovation procurement.
- During the OMC, announce the events in advanced to attract more suppliers.
- Guarantee a clear pre-understanding of the role of a PIN for all procurers and a common decision on what to include.
- When the PIN is joined, provide enough time to evaluate the PIN with the joined partners.
- Estimate an adjusted time and person-efforts to elaborate ITT documentation. Before drafting ITT documentation, it is important to have designed the whole phased PPI process, including all deliverables and templates required, as well as the rights and obligations of all parties.
- Shortage of time and difficulties in understanding PPI regulation in so many different EC countries is a barrier. PCP is above national legislation, but PPI requires legislations from each country, and this creates an

obstacle for European collaboration in a project like this. Funding from the procurers' organisations and ongoing budget is difficult to raise to the complex and risky process of a PPI in each member state.

- PPI shall not have a focus on national legislation but on the impact, it can have on learning results. Due to the complexity of all member states legislation, PPI seems more like a burden than an opportunity to many organisations. PPI is difficult for education due to the general small budget of the sector and it contains large risks, therefore, EU and other public funding is crucial to create some first cases that can be evaluated and learned from.

10. Cross-sectorial innovation procurement

Headline	Summary of content
Challenge identified	Lack of support on understanding and how approaches from other sectors can be applied in learning technology
How LEA overcome the challenge	Tools: pre-study on cross sectorial PCP
Results	One identified cross sectorial PCP case
Conclusions	Due to COVID the collaboration with Health care sector and common investments were not possible during spring 2020
Recommendations towards 2030	Investigate this model further to enable larger investments from procurers and to blend other technologies with the traditional learning technology

Table 14: Lack of knowledge on how other branches can be applied in learning technology

Challenge description

Value chain innovation is defined as the transformation of 'traditional' value chains into new ones - emerging industries - through cross-border and cross-sectoral

collaboration. New products and services, as well as new industrial sectors are not always the result of breakthrough innovation; they can be the result of value chain innovation. Such collaboration processes have become more and more visible on the European innovation policy radar due to their high potential in terms of innovation and economic growth.

The potentials of product improvements and cost reductions are in many cases already exhausted as for example in the learning technology industry. Considering growing complexity of learning environments, schools are not only looking for an even better solution, but for an easier one. But this direction of thought is what enterprises with a traditional culture of innovation consisting in continuous product improvement have trouble with. Having a look beyond the boundaries of one's own industry is becoming increasingly important. Cross-sectoral innovation can foster growth.

How LEA overcome the challenge

For the sector of education and from a buyers perspective LEA has initiated a study on how to use PCP to:

- Transfer approaches from other sectors into learning technology
- Gather larger sums of investments from more departments than education for resource efficiency

LEA gathered a working group with procurers from Sweden, Finland and Spain to investigate the opportunity of a cross sectorial PCP in March 2020.

The intention was to seek joint investments from educational, health and employment departments from three procurers on regional level addressing the market with one common and cross sectorial need – growing mental illness among young people in Europe.

Project name	Conversational Agents in Youth Mental Health Promotion CAMEo – PCP
Scope	Mental health, work and education - AI driven chatbots to assist Youth mental health
Overall challenge	Growing mental illness amongst young people in Europe creates; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk of exclusion in society on a personal level • Dropping out on an educational level • Increased costs in health sector on a societal level • Long term unemployment on a societal level Education, health care providers and employment sector could procure together
Partners	Minimum 3 procurers with a combined approach and representing different sectors, support and expert partners on technology, PCP and dissemination. Total of 10 partners maximum
Background and needs	All children and young people are a huge resource and at the same time there are all the more young persons who claim to be suffering from mental illness, and young persons who, for various reasons, risk ending up in vulnerable situations. Growing mental illness amongst young people is one of

	<p>the most serious public health challenges facing our European society. In the WHO European Region, depression and anxiety disorders fall into the top 5 causes of overall disease burden among children and adolescents (as measured by disability-adjusted life years). Suicide is the leading cause of death among 10–19 year-olds in low-and middle-income countries of the region, and the second-leading cause in high-income countries. Those responsible for following up young people with mental health problems are;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • School health service and pupil health service • Primary health care service • Specialist health care service • Other key players for employment and social security in the MS <p>Innovative technology to support a common approach to this challenge is needed to improve the wellbeing of the next generations European.</p>
--	--

Table 15: The CAMEo project description

Results

The pre- study resulted in reflections and opportunities on a complete new and unique collaboration. However due to Covid – 19 did not proceed to a real procurement within the framework of LEA. It is the intention of the buyers group identified to re- start the collaboration in September 2020 as a single project outside LEA's scope.

Recommendations towards 2030

Cross sectorial innovation procurement should definitely be investigated further as it can encourage schools and educational budgets to invest in innovative technology. Schools are often connected with health and other departments in a municipality and many challenges can be addressed jointly.

A good example is that in 2019 a Norwegian groups of 49 municipalities created a market dialogue with learning technology suppliers asking them to provide tools and service based upon Spotify and Netflix available technology to simplify the use for the students and teachers.

Traditional learning technology industry shall also seek to transfer innovations from other branches (entertainment and music, space, health etc.) to meet the expectations of students and teachers in Europe.

11. School labs and CO-CREATION

Headline	Summary of content
Challenge identified	Lack of dialogue between procurers and suppliers in order to understand needs and to implement new ideas for the edtech market
How LEA overcome the challenge and lessons learned	LEA involved schools, suppliers and experts in a needs analysis and the exchange of different models of school labs. The improvement of communication through different tools and media helped the dialogue
Related LEA actions to overcome Covid – 19 impact	Facebook group ‘Organizing teaching during COVID-19 crisis’ and launch of two tests in Turin EDU.LAB
Results	526 members in Facebook groups, hundreds of students involved in EDU.LAB tests.
Conclusions	School labs can boost the dialogue between schools and suppliers, guided and observed by experts
Recommendations towards 2030	Learning technologies could help our schools to be more flexible, adaptive and resilient, then procurement of Edtech should be innovative.

Table 16: The lack of dialogue between procurers and suppliers

The LEA project aimed at facing common challenges in real co-creation in schools, by designing open spaces of experimentation for procurers, suppliers, learn tech experts, teachers and students. According to Bovill (2019), LEA pursues co-creation as a new pedagogical idea that emphasises learner empowerment and fills the gap in between students’ involvement and partnership. Co-creation suggests an effective collaboration between teachers, experts, suppliers and students. Inside these proactive environments, students become active participants in the learning process, building knowledge and developing innovative solutions.

Challenge description

In the LEA framework, City of Turin enabled the EDU.LAB for two main reasons. Firstly, it has started from the assumption that there was an increasing interest among technology suppliers to bridge their innovative ideas with the real school

context. Secondly, the procurers expressed their willingness to set-up more effective procurements of learning technologies to provide widespread innovation among schools. In order to build this link, the City perceived the need to provide a physical space where learning technologies can be improved and developed through CO-CREATION processes. This led to the creation of EDU.LAB inside a middle school (11-14 ages), which makes 450 mq available for learning innovation. For the EDU.LAB experience the most relevant challenge was to explain what PPI and PCP are and involve people about procurement issue. In Konnevesi (Finland), teachers had the privilege to plan their working hours out of the lessons. In the attempt to design its co-creation strategy, the Finnish municipality had to deal with two main challenges. On the one hand, the local administration had to involve teachers and staff-members since the early phases of the lab, to build a common plan of implementation. On the others, to assure that cooperation was endorsed by all of them, further time for discussion between partners has been granted during the whole process.

The collection of information was the main challenge for ENTER (the European Network for Transfer and Exploitation of European Results), which had to provide research studies on LEA. From the OVGU (Otto-von-Guericke-Universität Magdeburg) perspective, the focus was managing the diversity of devices and infrastructure during the activities, to create comparable results between groups in different countries, and obtain the results from each participant in time.

How LEA overcome the challenge

The different challenges identified by the partners have been addressed by adopting a shared strategy. The City of Turin has designed a communication strategy in order to spell out the main objects and goals of EDU.LAB. This entailed preliminary workshops and informative materials. In Konnevesi, the City has involved teachers by offering them opportunities to take a part in LEA meetings (BETT in London and INTED in Valencia). It turned out to be a remarkable way to motivate teachers and stress the importance to share their experience throughout the community of learning experts. OVGU decided to spend more time on involvement and explanations to the users. ENTER worked on holding a steady and fruitful communication with each partner.

Even if the LEA partners adopted effective actions to overcome organisational and bureaucratic barriers, many clues and suggestions should be taken into account according with their lab experience. First, it is important to take teachers along to participate in LEA meetings. That is the easiest and best way to involve teachers as co-creators of the School Labs. Second, the designed action is marginally linked and included in a procurement strategy, therefore more insightful plans should be thought to bridge experimentations with the wider topic of procurement. Thirdly, a clear communication of short-period goals could help companies which would be keen to join LEA. As stated by all of the partners, even in the preliminary phase, it is a key factor to communicate precisely and clearly what to do and how to do it next. Finally, it is very important to have enough time for translations and evaluation of the material.

The spread out of COVID-19 has been jeopardizing LEA implementation throughout the European countries. However the partners turned out to be

responsive by opening a group on Facebook 'Organizing teaching during COVID-19 crisis'. This tool is helping all the partners to organise lessons and follow up the Labs, by collecting the best practices and suggestions on activating teaching methods. It represents a common platform for procurers, suppliers, experts and teachers dealing with learning technologies. Due to COVID-19 the vast majority of the experimentations has been interrupted. Nonetheless, in Turin, two companies joined EDU.LAB (*Vertical* and *Dktk 3d*) by proposing a virtual 3D tour of MAO, the Museum of Oriental Art, which can be enjoyed online by students of Turin schools. The tour entails a quiz game on the artworks and artefacts exposed in the museum to facilitate the learning process. Currently, the municipality is collecting the first data provided by teachers and students. In addition the City of Turin, joining the initiative "Skype in the Classroom" offered to schools the emotion of a field trip using the Teams platform of Microsoft. Classes were connected with museums and a didactic garden by video conference and they can discover those places by an interactive experience.

Results

The Facebook group 'Organizing teaching during COVID-19 crisis' has now 526 members and several posts from different countries with the aim to exchange experience and give help and ideas during Covid period.

The 3D tour of MAO was submitted to schools: 22 teachers and 130 students responded to questionnaire proposed. The 93.1% of the students want to repeat a similar experience in classroom. 16 virtual trips were conducted in local Museums and the didactic garden. 48 families responded to the proposed questionnaire and the majority said they were satisfied of the experience.

Ti piacerebbe fare questa visita virtuale in classe?
0 / 130 correct responses

E' in generale soddisfatt* dell'esperienza?
48 risposte

Figure 4: 3D tour of MAO questionnaire responses

A guideline on how to set up Edulab dedicated to schools and other public authorities was published on the website (December 2019). A film on Turin EDULABS and LEA school labs methodology was launched (June 2020).

Conclusions

Learning technologies turned out to be one of the most important tools to face COVID-19. The capacity to develop alternative ways of communication between teachers, students and developers, by playing a key-role to assure high quality education. These can trigger the creativity and valorise the differences. Places like school labs can boost the dialogue among schools and suppliers, guided and observed by experts.

Recommendations towards 2030

The LEA project suggested current weaknesses and highlighted the potential of learning technologies. On the one hand, it shows how the improvement of public procurement is closely linked with the capacity to design common strategies between suppliers, procurers and users. On the other, it highlights how learning technologies could help our schools to be more flexible, adaptive and resilient. And last but not least, innovative learning technologies can foster the conditions for making the learning process accessible and socially inclusive for everyone

12. Capacity building concepts

Table with summary of concept

Headline	Summary of content
Challenge identified	Need to accelerate knowledge transfer, dialogue and awareness-raising of innovation procurement within the learning technology sector.
How LEA overcome the challenge and lessons learned	Tools: Capacity Building Seminars (CBS), webinars and online materials available on LEA's website
Related LEA actions to overcome Covid – 19 impact	Webinars instead of live events

Results	1 internal CBS and 2 external CBS organized, over 80 persons attended the 3 seminars, and, as of 22 June 2020, the 24 webinars developed during the project had 1514 views.
Conclusions	CBS were important to the participants, since the level of knowledge about PCP and PPI processes is low, especially under the procurers group.
Recommendations towards 2030	Simplify processes and seminars; adopt more online webinars and make the physical CBS available to be assisted online; adapt content to different stakeholders; improve post satisfaction and evaluation survey process.

Table 17: Need to accelerate knowledge transfer, dialogue and awareness-raising of innovation procurement

Challenge description

To promote procurers' capacity building, enabling them to understand, prepare and use innovative procurement methods (PCP and PPI to procure innovative solutions for education), LEA developed and promoted a series of capacity building seminars, complemented with training materials, creating a body of knowledge to improve procurers' capacity to undergo in the future in processes of PCP and PPI.

The Capacity Building seminars are important for the decision makers and the procurement officers involved in the procurement process since they are responsible the planning and execution of the procurement and related activities (e.g. to conduct of market consultations, definition of technical specifications, preparation of tender documentation, evaluation of tenders and selection of successful bidders, as well as management and monitoring of the procurement contract(s)).

How LEA overcome the challenge

Method

In order to understand what were the main and more urgent needs to be addressed under the form of presentations at this first internal Capacity Building seminar, a voting was made by all the consortium members during the kick-off meeting. They voted on a list of 13 needs, classifying them as: 1- very important to learn about; 2-important to learn about; 3-not so important I already know about it. The topics with the most votes were presented at the seminar. After the internal CBS an online questionnaire was sent to all the participants to evaluate their satisfaction and to understand what could be improved to the future CBS.

The first CBS served as a pilot to the next external CBS and provided the LEA Consortium valuable recommendations for the upcoming external CBS. Based on the results achieved with the Satisfaction Surveys and the opinions provided by the presenters, there were outlined some recommendations and guidelines that helped improved the future external CBS.

After each external CBS, an online questionnaire was also sent online to all the participants to evaluate their satisfaction and to understand what could be improved in a future CBS.

Tools

- CBS
- Webinars
- Online Material
- Satisfaction survey

Lessons learned

The CBS total duration should be reconsidered, opting for a half-day seminar, including more hands-on exercises with the participants and more time for Q&A. Try to include as much successful business cases from PCP and/or PPI as possible, since it turned out to be a very valuable asset for the participants. Extra efforts should be carried out involving more local and national stakeholders, as they can bring practical examples and/or specific questions into the discussion. CBS could be upon invitation and pre-registration on the event. Keep the content of the CBS flexible and adaptable according to the type and level of knowledge of public and event, always used the developed materials in the best suitable way for the participants.

Results

Altogether one internal and two external CBSs were organised, while over 80 persons attended the three seminars. The satisfaction survey, answered by around a third of the participants, reveals that over 60% of the participants were completely satisfied with the events.

During the LEA project, online webinars were developed to introduce and discuss important concepts with experts. As of 30 of June 2020, the 24 webinars available had achieved 1514 views. In regards to publications, two reports related to capacity building seminars were created in the form of project deliverables. The first one (D5.1) contains a detailed description of the internal CBS implemented and recommendations for future CBS, while the second one (D5.2) contains a presentation of CBS and webinars delivered for external stakeholders and recommendations for the future. In addition, various PowerPoint materials to support CBS organisers were created, as well as one full paper presenting innovative procurement processes and how they can benefit the education sector (published in INTED2020 proceedings).

Conclusions

- The innovation procurement process and the responsible procurers must be well prepared. Seminars must be prepared to address participants with different levels of knowledge, trying to make the effort of leveraging the ones that know less about PCP and PPI, and knowing that this is always a continuous learning process until the end of the project.

- Every consortium must capitalise their internal expertise. Nevertheless, if there is a lack of expertise, independent experts must be invited to pass along their experience and knowledge.
- Investing in innovation procurement is not only challenging, but also requires a lot of preparation and time. Some tasks might look extremely time consuming and resource intensive, however, this is the price of being a pioneer in the field of innovation procurement in education.

Recommendations towards 2030

- Try to simplify. PCP and PPI are not easy to understand, so presentation must try to focus on the main topics in an easy common language, using visual graphics and examples whenever possible;
- PCP and PPI must be presented following a step by step methodology, from the preparation until the execution;
- Having independent experts is crucial to reinforce knowledge, and having external opinions is always a plus;
- Always try to have some previous experiences from other Projects on PCP and PPI, to collect lessons learnt;
- Save some time at the end of the presentations for Questions and Answers – participation is very welcome and benefits the both sides;
- Try to have shorter presentation covering more themes, to give participants a general overview of the whole process;
- Take into consideration the levels of knowledge that participants might have on the PCP and PPI topics;
- Try, whenever possible to have the presentations available or to be assisted online, for those who cannot be physically present.

13. Exploitation strategy 2020 and beyond

Table with summary of concept

Headline	Summary of content
Challenge identified	Risk that collaboration and exchange initiated by LEA-N ends when project ends.
How LEA overcome the challenge and lessons learned	Creation of an exploitation strategy, to secure motivation, ownership and leadership for the future of LEA-N.
Related LEA actions to overcome Covid – 19 impact	LEA-N webinar series positions network as space for finding solutions to new challenges for education, expected to continue in the medium to long-term.

Results	Exploitation Strategy co-developed with core LEA-N participants.
Conclusions	By co-developing an exploitation strategy, members can steer future plans to meet their real needs. Knowing the future direction also makes recruitment easier.
Recommendations towards 2030	LEA-N should be used as a multiplier and replicator of future education and learntech project activities.

Table 18: The risk that LEA-N collaboration ends with the project

Challenge description

As discussed in section 3, networking is an important source of support for procurers doing innovation procurement. Networks, however, can take various forms. Bakker and Walker (2008) identify two distinct structures for collaborative procurement networks:

- Formal and centralised – third party organisations are set up with the purpose of managing and coordinating collaboration, with formal rules and dedicated resources.
- Informal (and virtual) – member-owned and operate without (many) formal rules, without dedicated resources.

During the LEA project (Mar 2019- Jun 2020), networking among procurers has taken place under a centralised model. Partners met in person six times, and have participated in virtual meetings and webinars, each organised by the LEA project (coordinator and task leaders) – which can be considered a third party organisation – supported by project funding and governed by a project grant agreement.

The challenge for the medium to long-term sustainability of the LEA-Network will be moving from a formal and centralised form of organising, to an informal and decentralised network.

How LEA overcome the challenge

To survive such a transition, **motivation**, a sense of **ownership** and **leadership** will be required. As such, ICLEI began work on an Exploitation Strategy in July 2019. The Exploitation Strategy aimed to outline the steps necessary for continued collaboration in the medium to long-term, preparing the ground and providing a framework to structure the LEA-N after the project has ended.

The Exploitation Strategy was developed in three rounds.

- Round 1: an initial draft was prepared by ICLEI (based on their experience in establishing procurer networks), with feedback from JYU (as project coordinator), EUPK (as LEA-N task leader). Initial input was then collected from partners at a telephone conference on 28th of October, and during a workshop at the Turin partner meeting on December 4th.
- Round 2: based on feedback, a second version of the Exploitation Strategy was shared for comments on 12 December 2020.

- Round 3: based on comments received, a third version of the Exploitation Strategy was shared, and an online meeting hosted on 19th February 2020 in order to finalise its contents.

The final Exploitation Strategy sets out the following:

- Purpose of LEA-N: during the project, LEA-N's purpose has been defined by the Key Performance Indicators set in the LEA Baseline (June 2018) and updated in the LEA Action Plan (October 2019). These focus on the participation of procurers in project activities – including the Procurement Challenge Tool and a LEA-N event (reorganised as a series of webinars). The Exploitation Strategy has defined a purpose beyond the end of the project, based on procurers own reported needs and wants, in order to incentivise continued **motivation** to participate.
- LEA-N membership: in the short term, membership of LEA-N is defined by the project KPIs, and limited to procurers. It was agreed with LEA-N members, however, that non-procuring members of the LEA consortium can also be considered LEA-N members in the post-project period, to continue beneficial collaboration (for example, injecting the network with expertise and connecting the network with future funding opportunities). Discussions of how to integrate new LEA-N members also helped to establish **ownership** among existing members and inspire new ideas for developing this in new members.
- LEA-N Governance: to ensure initial continuation of activities, it has been agreed that JYU will chair the network. Options for future chairing configurations are also included, to ensure continued **leadership**. A framework for running the network is also established as a guide, including suggestions for how and when to organise meetings, communicate internally and externally, and manage resources and methodologies developed in LEA.
- It was agreed that LEA will continue webinars about once a month on the second Wednesday of the month at 10:30CET. All partners can propose topics, news and guests and JYU will be the webinar host. SERN will provide platform.
- LEA Support hub and website will be online for at least 5 years onwards on ENTER's server (domain is registered by JYU) and minimum updates can be made to the stable content. However, ENTER will provide access to the website blog for all partners to share news with LEA network
- New members can join and they are curated by JYU and ENTER.
coordinator@learntechaccelerator.eu will still work

Results

The creation of an Exploitation Strategy, co-developed with LEA-N's core members (the LEA project partners) setting out their intentions for the post-project period.

Conclusions

By projecting the medium- and long-term direction of the network, it was easier to establish motivations for participating in the Procurement Challenge Tool and LEA-N event (thus meeting KPIs).

By creating the Exploitation Strategy using a collaborative approach, in language which is meaningful to the target audience, a greater sense of ownership is created, and procurers feel more empowered to recruit new members.

Recommendations towards 2030

LEA-N can act as a multiplier and replicator of future education and learntech project activities. It is a unique group focused on a topic which has never been more relevant, due to the COVID-19 crisis. Procurers can continue to exchange their lessons and seek partners for joint activities through the structures which LEA-N has put in place.

14. Final words - Education, innovation procurement and innovative purchase methods upfront 2030

A critical mass is a sufficient number of adopters of a new idea, technology or innovation in a social system so that the rate of adoption becomes self-sustaining and creates further growth. LEA offers a good start of such a critical mass and conditions under which reciprocal behaviour can be started within educational groups to become self-sustaining.

As of the 30th June 2020, 72 procuring organisations have actively participated in LEA-N activities, from 16 EU Member States. Countries (and number of LEA-N members) include Austria (2), Belgium (3), Bulgaria (1), Croatia (1), Cyprus (1), Finland (16), Germany (3), Hungary (3), Italy (16), Netherlands (2), Poland (2), Portugal (4), Romania (1), Slovenia (1), Spain (9), Sweden (4), as well as 1 member from Switzerland.

In total, 106 people from 91 organisations participated in the LEA-N webinar series, including 35 procurers from 15 Member States.

Awareness of innovation procurement as a tool for accelerating learntech adoption in schools is in a nascent phase. The LEA-Network has done valuable work to raise awareness of innovation procurement as a tool in the education sector, and make visible the demand for innovative learntech to the market. LEA-N is a unique group focused on a topic which has never been more relevant, due to the COVID-19 crisis. Via the Procurement Challenge Tool, the project has created a space where procurers can continue to share and exchange, and propose areas for future collaboration and joint procurement. The agreement in the medium term of continued exchange and governance for the LEA-N (via the Exploitation Strategy) will preserve the foundation laid by LEA for future work in this topic area, ensuring that LEA-N can act as a multiplier and replicator of future education and learntech project activities.

LEA lessons learned, LEA Roadmap 2030 and key message films, intend to make available the findings and conclusions developed in the framework of the project

to other procurers, business, experts or professionals interested in procurement of learntech as well as to disseminate the potential innovation procurement can have in the development of Learntech that respond to the real needs of final users. The LEA films are:

LEA-N Buyers network:
https://www.youtube.com/watch?time_continue=3&v=gV31oDmWV3Q&feature=emb_logo

PPI in 4 steps: Public Procurement on Innovation in Education:
https://www.youtube.com/watch?time_continue=2&v=GAQZeDKYsmY&feature=emb_logo

PCP in 5 steps: Pre-commercial Procurement in Education:
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zyetvgQicV0&feature=emb_logo

LEA-School-labs: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=S9i9vnybEKk&feature=emb_logo

Innovation procurement in education:
https://www.youtube.com/watch?time_continue=1&v=Dvwab0aQab8&feature=emb_logo

By using the network created, tools and methods created LEA can serve as a “start engine” for the traditional education sector to become more self-sustaining, and hopefully within a couple of years with no more needs on additional external investments by different EU funds.

Once again and as stated in the introduction of this roadmap, digitalisation of schools is based upon the following three processes and steps;

1. Purchase / procurement process
2. Implementation process
3. Management process

If the first step of purchase and procurement results in the “wrong” digital products and systems, the following two steps will automatically fail. To put it simply, to be successful and reach increased learning results in the digital age, we need to start by building competence and capacity in the digital purchase and procurement process. Hence it is the vision of LEA that Ministries of Education (MoE) of each member state shall seek to learn more and act as umbrella organisations in their own countries create capacity building in their countries using the LEA tools, templates and models presented and summarized on the last page.

Buyers of learning technology shall join LEA-N Buyers network to form a stronger critical mass that can influence and align the market with real needs

Buyers of learning technology shall interact with the LEA procurement tool to

create common EU demand and jointly address the market
Suppliers of learning technology shall use the country profiles and support hub https://www.learntechaccelerator.eu/lea_n/ to learn more about procurement in different EU member states
Schools and buyers of learning technology shall learn from LEA market foresight to be able to buy and demand solutions of tomorrow and not from yesterday
Schools and buyers of learning technology shall seek to use the templates made for PCP and PPI in education as well as get inspired by the unique model of cross -sectorial innovation procurement
Schools shall be inspired by LEA school labs to create venues where the market and students can meet and CO-CREATE the technology of tomorrow
Organisations from across the EU shall be motivated to use the capacity building material LEA has created on the novel topics of innovation procurement for schools
Organisations from across the EU shall seek to advantages of LEA exploitation strategy and the knowledge gathered using experts, online course material, films and webinars way beyond LEA project ends

Table 19: Summary of recommendations from LEA roadmap

By using this roadmap for guidance and support **innovation procurement** shall be considered for good co-creation business model that can put European schools in the driving seat of Education, steering towards UN SDG 4 in 2030!

Thank you for your attention - LEA team June 2020

